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GreenCharge Project Deliverable: D8.1

Communication Strategy and Plan

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About GreenCharge

GreenCharge takes us a few important steps closer to achieving one of the dreams of modern cities: a zero-emission transport system based on electric vehicles running on green energy, with traffic jams and parking problems becoming things of the past. The project promotes:

Power to the people! The GreenCharge dream can only be achieved if people feel confident that they can access charging infrastructure as and when they need it. So GreenCharge is developing a smart charging system that lets people book charging in advance, so that they can easily access the power they need.

The delicate balance of power If lots of people try to charge their vehicles around the same time (e.g. on returning home from work), public electricity suppliers may struggle to cope with the peaks in demand. So we are developing software for automatic energy management in local areas to balance demand with available supplies. This balancing act combines public supplies and locally produced reusable energy, using local storage as a buffer and staggering the times at which vehicles get charged.

Getting the financial incentives right Electric motors may make the wheels go round, but money makes the world go round. So we are devising and testing business models that encourage use of electric vehicles and sharing of energy resources, allowing all those involved to cooperate in an economically viable way.

Showing how it works in practice GreenCharge is testing all of these innovations in practical trials in Barcelona, Bremen and Oslo. Together, these trials cover a wide variety of factors: *vehicle type* (scooters, cars, buses), *ownership model* (private, shared individual use, public transport), *charging locations* (private residences, workplaces, public spaces, transport hubs), *energy management* (using solar power, load balancing at one charging station or within a neighbourhood, battery swapping), and *charging support* (booking, priority charging).

To help cities and municipalities make the transition to zero emission/sustainable mobility, the project is producing three main sets of results: (1) *innovative business models*; (2) *technological support*; and (3) *guidelines* for cost efficient and successful deployment and operation of charging infrastructure for Electric Vehicles (EVs).

The *innovative business models* are inspired by ideas from the sharing economy, meaning they will show how to use and share the excess capacity of private renewable energy sources (RES), private charging facilities and the batteries of parked EVs in ways that benefit all involved, financially and otherwise.

The *technological support* will coordinate the power demand of charging with other local demand and local RES, leveraging load flexibility and storage capacity of local stationary batteries and parked EVs. It will also provide user friendly charge planning, booking and billing services for EV users. This will reduce the need for grid investments, address range/charge anxiety and enable sharing of already existing charging facilities for EV fleets.

The *guidelines* will integrate the experience from the trials and simulations and provide advice on localisation of charging points, grid investment reductions, and policy and public communication measures for accelerating uptake of electromobility.

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Executive Summary

This document explains the communication strategy of the project and presents the contribution and cooperation expected from the partners. The aim of the Communication Strategy and Plan is to ensure a well-balanced communication towards the target audiences, the media and the public to achieve GreenCharge's project objectives. The Communication Strategy and Plan starts with general information about the communication objectives and strategy as well as internal and external communication. For all communication actions it is essential to refer to the H2020 funding by the EU and to the CIVITAS network for cities dedicated to cleaner and better transport in Europe and beyond.

The GreenCharge strategy covers the key audiences, which are three defined value chains (charging, energy, electric vehicles), academic institutions, cities and policy makers and the public/society in general and their key messages. GreenCharge key messages are:

- Existing grid capacity at housings can be equipped with charging points.
- GreenCharge stakeholders can reduce their energy bill and do something good for the environment.
- Through GreenCharge, smart grid providers can see a market opportunity in ESNs. Working closely together with other parties in optimising grid load and charging pricing can be a win-win situation for all, EV users included.
- GreenCharge ensures that citizens' quality of life will be improved, if less pollutants and less noise accrue with more people using EVs.

Special communication planning tools will be developed to manage, monitor and report about all activities. The central source for information is the GreenCharge website (www.greencharge2020.eu) for the general public and the SharePoint Intranet for consortium members. Communication tools include also social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, vimeo), brochures, presentations, lectures of students and academics, a video, webinars, websites and social media of project partners. The content will be presented in newsletters, publications, press-releases and external and self-organised events.

GreenCharge will cooperate and exploit synergies with other groups like initiatives to facilitate the exchange of best practices and the deployment of new technologies at the local (city) level (e.g. the Covenant of Mayors, the Smart Cities and Communities European Innovation Partnership and the CIVITAS initiative), the EU Platform on Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans and the European Alternative Fuels Observatory.

From this strategy, a general communication plan that involves activities of all project partners throughout the entire project will be produced. A yearly detailed plan will be prepared to better coordinate the activities of the consortium. The deliverable also gives advice to partners on how to use the main social media channels. Finally, the document also presents an overview of events in which the project members will be represented. Project members have identified a clear set of key performance indicators to evaluate the performance of the communication activities.

This document may be revised after formal delivery, and/or augmented with separate mechanisms for detailed information (such as tables and lists stored in the cooperation tool used by the consortium). Any such revisions will be made available on request.

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List of Abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CS	Communication Strategy
ESN	Energy Smart Neighbourhood
EV	Electric Vehicle
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
RTO	Research and Technology Organization
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SUMPs	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans
V2G	Vehicle-to-grid

1 About the Deliverable “Communication Strategy and Plan”

1.1 Purpose of this deliverable

The development of the Communication Strategy and Plan (D8.1) is the basis to maximise the impact of the GreenCharge project and its results. Its purpose is to make sure that appropriate activities are undertaken to inform, engage, create awareness of and promote information about the project, its aims, its funding source, and its outputs. There will be an emphasis on communicating the wider societal and regulatory implications of GreenCharge, and their relevance to citizens. Therefore, it is necessary to build and maintain effective communication within the project and to the identified stakeholders. This activity will run through the entire lifespan of the project (M1-M36).

This deliverable report has been set up to be used by the consortium to

- (i) inform the public and targeted audiences about the communication actions;
- (ii) serve as a guide for the project partners to plan their individual communication actions, while respecting project standards and rules;
- (iii) define the related management, monitoring and reporting activities; and
- (iv) serve as a guide for any media and public relations activities in which the consortium is engaged.

The expected content of the deliverable (as defined in the Grant Agreement) is shown on the front cover of this document, in the field labelled “Deliverable Description”.

The content of the deliverable is entirely in line with the Grant Agreement, there are no deviations.

1.2 Intended audience of the communication strategy and plan

This deliverable is interesting for all project partners of GreenCharge and all stakeholders that wish to connect with the consortium or simply get informed about the project and its communication actions. The target audiences, key messages and communication means are defined in this document, for each target audience (such as cooperative housing associations, other building owners, smart grid providers, cities, charging operators and OEMs).

For the project partners, it provides guidance for communication planning and realisation.

1.3 Other project deliverables that may be of interest

This deliverable is based on inputs from the following deliverable:

- D3.1 Stakeholder Analysis: this document presents the result of the stakeholder analysis, identifying the concerns and needs from all stakeholders relevant for GreenCharge.

The deliverable describes different measures for communication. One of them is newsletter.

- D8.4 Newsletters: will be a collection 6 releases of newsletter planned in the project.

This deliverable describes an initial plan of communication activities. Subsequent completed and planned communication activities will be documented in the following deliverables:

- D8.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (V1): will describe the completed and planned communication activities to give an updated overview by M10.
- D8.3 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (V2): will describe the completed and planned communication activities to give an updated overview by M34.
- D8.6 High Impact Communication Report: will document all high impact communication activities implemented during the project course.

1.4 Other projects and initiatives

GreenCharge will use other projects and initiatives to intensify the communication range. GreenCharge will use the relationship among all partners, especially with ICLEI, clustering with other RDI projects, the CIVITAS initiative, Uptake Cities Group and local reference groups, as follows:

Relationships with project partner ICLEI: GreenCharge will, through ICLEI, establish communication partnerships with existing and relevant projects, stakeholder communities and networks. These pre-existing groups (such as CIVITAS or the Informed Cities group) already have the necessary communication infrastructure in place and therefore they can help GreenCharge to quickly reach our targeted audiences to promote the GreenCharge project and its impact. In our experience such pre-existing groups are very happy to support new innovations through their own communication platforms if they see the potential value for their stakeholders. The major advantage of working with these groups is that they are already known and trusted by the stakeholders they work with and, therefore, they can be of great help to get key messages to target audiences.

Clustering with other RDI projects: The project will liaise with other relevant RDI projects and also other initiatives at a European level to exchange results and knowledge and to learn from each other. The stakeholder analysis already revealed interesting related projects worthwhile to connect with.

The CIVITAS initiative: The project will liaise with the CIVITAS initiative by joining thematic CIVITAS platforms and using CIVITAS channels for dissemination (Bremen is funding member). To promote the CIVITAS initiative, the project will share the project's lessons and conclusions with cities both inside and outside of the consortium. Upon request, GreenCharge will cooperate with the CIVITAS-secretariat and participate in CIVITAS-lead activities. Further details will be specified in a Memorandum of Understanding that will be agreed between us and CIVITAS SATELLITE, the Coordination and Support Action, that supports the CIVITAS initiative.

Uptake Cities Group: Intensive exchange between the 3 pilot cities and the 12 Uptake Cities will generate peer-to-peer feedback and added value to the new business models developed for each city and give input to the roadmaps for replication developed by the 12 Uptake Cities.

Local Reference Groups: Local Reference Groups will be established at the beginning of the project, involving representatives from relevant associations, councils, and other entities/alliances that represent relevant businesses who are potential adopters. These groups will be consulted at each critical step of the project to provide feedback from a user's perspective.

2 Strategy and communication objectives and rules

The development of the **Communication Strategy and Plan** is part of WP8 – “Maximisation of Impact”. The overall objective of the communication activities is to broadly inform targeted audiences about the project. Therefore, it is necessary to build and maintain an effective communication within the project and to ensure large spreading of the project results to the industry community, the scientific community, policy makers and the broad public.

This specific deliverable describes the strategy regarding the communication of GreenCharge objectives, activities, results, and the involved project partners. The goal of a coherent strategy is to ensure that the project’s content and outcomes will be widespread to the targeted stakeholders, at appropriate times and based on an appropriate methodology. This activity will run through the whole execution of the project (M1-M36). The communication strategy will serve as a guide for any media and public relations activity in which the consortium is engaged.

2.1 Communication objectives

This deliverable helps to meet the following objectives of WP8 regarding communication:

- To maximise the impact of the GreenCharge project outcomes within and beyond its lifespan
- To transfer the project results to relevant stakeholders including policy makers, industry and society via a systematic communication strategy so that lessons learned from the pilots have a major impact in helping decision makers throughout Europe
- To make sure that the technologies and business models developed in the project, and the lessons learned from the pilots, are made widely known and available to all relevant stakeholders
- To facilitate effective project internal and external communication

According to the European Commission participant portal website¹, the term communication is defined as follows:

Communication: Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

2.2 The communication strategy

The communication strategy defines what the consortium wishes to share with the public and the stakeholder groups the consortium will reach. All communication actions will be realised with the purpose to achieve these project goals:

- **Establishing the GreenCharge “Brand” within the EU:** It concerns not a brand in the sense of a consumer product, but rather a widely-known “household name” associated with a widely-supported positive goal. The GreenCharge brand could act as a reference for smart charging and Energy Smart Neighbourhoods (ESNs) in the European Union.
- **Synchronisation with EC Communication Activities:** To co-operate actively in events and initiatives organised by the European Commission for promotion of H2020 activities. The goal is to become a highly visible showcase project for H2020.
- **High public visibility:** While GreenCharge will of course address specialist and technical audiences, there will also be a major emphasis on addressing policy makers and cities.
- **Political inspiration by leading examples:** GreenCharge aims to provide an easy to reference political example supported by implementing objectives of the EU Transport White Paper and the Urban Mobility Package (SUMP).

¹ European Commission participant portal, <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal>

- **Increased reputation of EU funded projects:** The aim of the communication strategy is to reach out to society as a whole, while demonstrating how EU funding is used to tackle societal challenges while generating business for (local) entrepreneurs. GreenCharge will establish these goals by publications and seeking media attention. GreenCharge will use several communication channels for reaching out different stakeholder groups, including citizens.

The GreenCharge communication strategy will contemplate:

- Specific communication tools to be developed (i.e. website, press release, newsletters, etc.) with clear responsibilities attributed to each partner.
- Communication measures to be adopted (i.e. identification of industrial workshops, conferences to be attended, etc.).
- Target audiences to communicate the project results.

As in all projects, communication in GreenCharge is about promoting the project itself. But communication also has a second and critical double role: to positively influence the acceptance of eMobility, smart charging and ESNs. The communication strategy will focus on contacting, informing and engaging different stakeholder groups, based on the outcomes of the stakeholder analysis. Diverse information regimes will be applied to different stakeholders, based on the importance they have for the project and their interest in the outcomes of GreenCharge as derived from the stakeholder analysis. The identified stakeholder groups with a different interest on the project are:

- Cooperative housing associations and other building owners
- EV drivers/owners/fleet operators
- Electric Vehicles (EVs) drivers, owners and fleet operators
- Smart grid providers
- Charging operators
- Cities & policy makers
- OEMs along the EVs value chain
- Citizens

The communication strategy is built on the prioritization of certain groups of stakeholders. This will initially be decided directly within the consortium, which based on their joint competences can decide what external stakeholders are really needed. The stakeholder analysis will complement this prioritization by gathering information from all relevant stakeholders, among others by assessing their interest and influence on the project.

At the beginning of the project, there will be only generic news to share and communication will be focused on making stakeholders aware of the project. In this phase, GreenCharge will deploy generic communication channels, like the website and periodic newsletters with generic information about the project. As GreenCharge progresses, project results become available and more insights are obtained, stakeholders should be more closely involved in the project. The information that will become available provides the opportunity to involve external stakeholders into the project by changing their perceived interest and attitude with targeted information. The dissemination measures to be deployed thus depend on the position a stakeholder has towards the project.

2.3 Internal and external communication

Depending on who a project member is talking to, there are two ways to communicate: internal and external communication.

Internal communication. Internal communication is the communication among the consortium partners and communication between the consortium as a whole and the EU. The communication between the consortium and the EU will go via the consortium project manager and the EU project officer. The way in which project members should communicate to each other is described in the Project Handbook (D1.2).

External communication. External communication is the communication with people or organisations outside the consortium. For the external communication every project member should follow the description below to be in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement.

According to the Grant Agreement “Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

For communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769016”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769016”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem (see **Figure 2-1**) must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.”

As the GreenCharge project members acknowledge and share the CIVITAS objectives, the cooperation is to be shown in displaying the CIVITAS logo (see **Figure 2-2**) next to the EU emblem.

Both logos must be published on all of the communication materials of the project. This includes the deliverables and communication materials (such as brochures and roll-ups) and on presentation templates. The EU logo is always displayed in first place and should not displayed smaller than the CIVITAS logo.

Figure 2-1: EU emblem² Figure 2-2: CIVITAS logo

The EU emblem and the CIVITAS logos will be stored on the document management system of the project, as well as all communication material produced.

² Different formats of the emblems are available here: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

3 Target audiences and messages

3.1 Target audiences and key messages

GreenCharge audience goes from stakeholders in three defined value chains (see below) over academic institutions, cities and policy makers to the public/society in general. The messages to transmit, or type of engagement to seek, are different for each type of audience.

Figure 3-1: The GreenCharge value chains

The main target audiences selected by the consortium, to which the project will communicate about the GreenCharge project, the communication pathways and channels for each one are summarized in Table 2.

In the course of the project, the group of stakeholders will be validated and expanded, if needed, to react adequately to new market trends or new business models.

Table 2: Overview of the target audiences and their key messages

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
Charging facility manufacturer	Producing charging points	Increasing the need for public/private charging points	There is a need for guaranteed availability of charging points.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Charging facility retailer	Selling charging points	Increasing the need for public/private charging points	There is a need for guaranteed availability of charging points.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Charging facility operator	Providing electricity for charging (L)EVs	Increasing the usage of (L)EVs.	Charging operators can be assisted with technology for booking to support load balancing and seamless use of different charging operators.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
Charging services	Providing a booking and/or billing system	Increasing the usage of booking/billing systems.	Charging services can be assisted with technology for booking to support load balancing and seamless use of different charging operators.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Energy producer	Producing and selling energy	Increasing the need for green energy, usage of energy instead of fossil fuels.	Increasing usage of EVs will increase energy demand. Usage of local RES (micro grids) is needed to obtain the sustainable objectives of the project.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
Energy distributor	Distributing the energy via a reliable network.	Increasing the need for green energy, usage of energy instead of fossil fuels. ESNs as a new market opportunity.	Smart grid providers can see a market opportunity in ESNs. Working closely together with other parties in optimising grid load and charging pricing can be a win-win situation for all, EV users included.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Energy storage	Providing storage possibilities for redundant energy.	Increasing the need for green energy. Usage of V2G technology.	Local RES can be used optimally if there are possibilities for storing energy. There is a need for energy storage if V2G	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
			technology is used.															
Energy management	Providing a reliable energy network without power failures due to peak electricity demands.	Energy storage and load balancing will play a large role for using RES.	Usage of smart charging systems in combination with energy storage possibilities will make it possible to cope with peak demands.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EV component manufacturer	Selling EV components	Increasing the use of EVs.	Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) opportunities will be an advantage to ESNs and indirectly promote the use of EVs.	X	X	X	X	X	X					X	X	X		X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
			A guaranteed availability of charging points will boost the use of EVs.															
EV manufacturer	Selling EV’s	Increasing the use of EVs.	<p>Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) opportunities will be an advantage to ESNs and indirectly promote the use of EVs.</p> <p>A guaranteed availability of charging points will boost the use of EVs.</p>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Fleet operator	Reducing their carbon footprint,	Carsharing can be a solution for parking	Booking systems for charging and use of shared	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific publication	Scientific publication	Short announcement
	contributing to company’s sustainability plan, offering “green” alternatives to customers, be first mover in a sector	problems. Charging, booking and billing systems will ease the use of shared EVs.	EVs will ease the use of EVs and will fix the problem of charge anxiety.															
Providing funding	Return on investments.	Smart charging and booking systems will ease the use of EVs.	Easing the use of EVs will increase the use of EVs and will make it possible to increase the return on investments for funding providers.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X
Providing knowledge	Sharing their knowledge.	Evaluation of the three pilots will provide	Spreading lessons learned from the	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
		useful information about the transition to zero-emission mobility.	GreenCharge project															
Providing regulation	Avert that the new mobility (e.g. shared cars, charging points) will turn into a chaos or get delayed due to a lack of regulations.	Regulation providers will play an important role for making the transition to zero-emission mobility possible in an orderly manner.	New types of mobility do require new regulations at the national and local level. Clear regulations will speed up the innovation process.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
cooperative housing associations and other	Being an attractive house owner, attracting	Additional service for tenants; better ecological	Existing grid capacity at housings can be equipped with charging points.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific Scientific publication	Short announcement	
building owners	new residents. Making extra revenue.	footprint; “green” image	Stakeholders can reduce their energy bill and do something good for the environment.															
Local authorities	Better living in cities, Less emissions. Better public health.	More and more people are willing to use EVs if more charging points exist. Cities and policy makers must be informed about the potential of ESNs to facilitate more charging points.	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) must include plans for charging infrastructure. To increase attention of ESNs.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Citizens	Easy to use transportation (for a	A guaranteed charging availability will	Citizens quality of life will be improved with	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X	X	X		X

Target audiences	What are their interests?	Unique “selling points” of GreenCharge?	Key messages	Communication pathways and channels														
				Website	Newsletters	Brochures	Presentations	Social media	movie/animation	External Events	GreenCharge conference	Open days	Workshops	Webinars	Blog entry	Non-scientific publication	Scientific publication	Short announcement
	<p>reasonable price).</p> <p>Less emissions and better public health.</p>	<p>decrease charging anxiety.</p> <p>Booking and billing systems will make it much easier to use a (shared) EV.</p> <p>As a energy prosumer, you will earn money if there is redundant energy.</p>	<p>more people using EVs.</p> <p>Using (shared) EVs is an easy to use transportation mode due to charging and booking systems.</p>															

4 Communication tools

4.1 Website

A new project website (see Figure 4-1) completely devoted to the GreenCharge project has been set up with a direct, simple and easy to remember URL, which reminds the acronym of the project:

<https://www.greencharge2020.eu/>.

The GreenCharge website, implemented at M4, will be continuously updated and will remain life for three years after the project so that results continue to be available. The website provides a place where the open parts of the detailed knowledge generated in the project can be accessed directly by users. This includes public project deliverables, detailed technical specifications, copies or links to scientific publications / conference proceedings, etc. Downloading those articles by the public at large will be granted for free. The website will also provide information on how the project's open research data can be accessed (it will not be stored on the website itself). The main sections and their subsections that are available to each user are listed here:

- Home
- About: Project – Consortium – Partner Project – Uptake Cities
- Pilot Sites: Overview of Pilots – Barcelona – Bremen – Oslo
- Project Outputs: Deliverables – Public Materials – Videos – Newsletters
- News & Events: News – Events
- Contact

In Figure 4-1, Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-3 some screenshots of the homepage, pilot description page and the news & events page are showed. The website will contribute to increase GreenCharge's visibility and establishing the GreenCharge brand. The website publishes information about what is planned and what has been achieved in the project, who is involved, and the role of H2020 activities and funding, newsletters, webinars, animated videos, etc. will be on the website. There will be sections addressing different audiences: citizens, industry, policy makers, researchers, etc. Special attention will be given to making the site relevant to each target group. Google Analytics is being used to measure external interest in the site, and the data thus gathered is being carefully monitored. All necessary edits to the GreenCharge website for SEO have been made. In addition, all partners will be asked to link to the GreenCharge website from their websites to improve it for Search Engine Optimization.

The GreenCharge website also provides the possibility to subscribe to the newsletter via the subscription form. People who are interested can subscribe to receive the GreenCharge newsletter in their email. The newsletter will increase the engagement of the stakeholders and will help to expand the stakeholder community. Information about the newsletter content and structure can be found in paragraph 4.3.

- Home
- About
- Pilot Sites
- Project Outputs
- News & Events
- Contact

3 Pilot living labs

Figure 4-1: Homepage of the GreenCharge website

- Home
- About
- Pilot Sites**
- Project Outputs
- News & Events
- Contact

Figure 4-2: Oslo pilot description on the GreenCharge website

Home

About

Pilot Sites

Project Outputs

News & Events

Contact

Figure 4-3: News and events page on the GreenCharge website

4.2 Publications & Press-releases

A press and media relations campaign will be implemented, ensuring media interest and coverage from the outset of GreenCharge and throughout its duration. This will significantly raise public awareness and increase GreenCharge visibility.

The following reviewed Journals (publisher) – several provide open access options, are identified:

- Elsevier Energy
- IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid
- Elsevier Applied Energy

These scientific publications fall under the dissemination actions, for which special rules are defined regarding open access to the publication, but also to bibliographic metadata of all forms of published output. This is dealt with in the dissemination and exploitation activities and related deliverable D8.2.

Other publications / magazines (publisher) to be applicable for GreenCharge are:

- Public Transport International (<http://www.uitp.org/pti>)
- Renewable World Magazine (<http://www.renewableenergyworld.com/magazines.html>)
- PV Magazine Worldwide (<https://www.pv-magazine.com/>)
- CleanTechnica (<https://cleantechnica.com/cleantechnica/>)
- Fleet Europe Magazine °90 Special Smart Mobility Management
- Energy Storage (<https://www.energy-storage.news/news/list>)
- The Parking Professional Magazine (<http://www.parking.org/news-publications/the-parkingprofessional-magazine/>)
- Duurzaam Bedrijfsleven (<https://www.duurzaambedrijfsleven.nl/>)
- Parking News (<http://www.parking-net.com/parking-news>)

All publications will be collected in a document on the project management system and summarized in tables dedicated tables (

Table 3 and Table 4).

Table 3: List of Publications

No.	Publication date (DD.MM.YYYY)	Partner	Type of publication ³	Place of Publication	Main content	Link / Additional Information

Table 4: Additional list for scientific publications

No.	Type of scientific publication ⁴	Title	DOI	Repository Link	Link to the publication	ISSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number, date or frequency of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Is / Will open access provided to this publication ⁵	Peer-reviewed publication (No, Yes)	Joint public / private publication (No, Yes)	Notes

4.3 Newsletters

News and updates of the project will be distributed via newsletters. The aim is to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the latest project’s developments. Six newsletters will be issued, two newsletters per year, and distributed across Europe to an existing and further enlarged mailing list of 200+ recipients from local government, academia, business, NGOs and other relevant stakeholders, which make use of the already established e-newsletter 'Informed Cities' (heritage of the FP7 project PRIMUS), as well as to all other project partners' dissemination channels.

Newsletter Audience and Concept

The Newsletters must contain meaningful content for professionals as well as assisting in promoting the GreenCharge project. The newsletter is less focused on experts in the field but more focused on building a general understanding and acceptance of e-mobility, priming actors to be more involved in this field in the future (such as those involved in transport planning but without detailed e-mobility plans) as well as others in adjoining sectors (such as building and planning) who could be more involved in enabling the effective delivery of e-mobility measures if their overall knowledge and competence in the field was greater.

For detailed and complex project findings and information, the newsletter will refer to deliverables hosted on the website and other sources of information. The newsletter itself is not intended to be a technical document,

³ Blog entry, Non-scientific publication, Scientific publication, Short announcement

⁴ Article in journal, Publication in conference proceeding/workshop, Books/Monographs, Chapters in books, Thesis/dissertation, Other

⁵ Yes - Green Open Access, Yes - Gold Open Access, No

and this is reinforced by the fact it will use the broad Informed Cities newsletter as a springboard for its dissemination.

Dissemination Channels

The GreenCharge newsletter will be disseminated as follows:

- Via a link contained within Informed Cities newsletters
- Via links on social media
- Via direct ‘ad hoc’ emails to professional contacts of the Consortium partners
- Via passive browsing on the Newsletter page of the GreenCharge website

Newsletter structure

The GreenCharge newsletter uses a consistent three pages structure and will be issued six times during the project. The GreenCharge consortium has listed seven editorial principles for the newsletter content. The content should be:

- Short
- Non-technical
- Engaging
- Set within a real world context
- Colorful
- Enjoyable to read
- Easy to read on screen as mail chimp produced HTML

The structure of the three newsletter pages is displayed in table 5 (page 1), table 6 (page 2) and table 7 (page 3). A consistent structure does make it easier to plan the newsletter and to collect the right information from the consortium partners.

Table 5: Structure of newsletter page 1

Section	Content
Header	Project title and logo
	Date and issue number
	Newsletter theme/topic title
Body	Introduction from the coordinator or a work package leader
	Feature news article (see schedule in table 8)
Footer	Link to website and social media channels
	Contact details (for newsletter and project)
	Appropriate references to CIVITAS & H2020

Table 6: Structure of newsletter page 2

Section	Content
Header	Project title and logo
	Date and issue number
Body	Feature news article (continued from page 1)
	World news (controversies and innovation, short stories and links to the outside world)
Footer	Link to website and social media channels
	Contact details (for newsletter and project)
	Appropriate references to CIVITAS & H2020

Table 7: Structure of newsletter page 3

Section	Content
Header	Project title and logo
	Date and issue number
Body	Uptake cities profile (2 of 12 cities)
	Links to further news stories on the website (list)
	Latest project publications (list)
	Project diary (internal and opportunities for involvement)
	Puzzle (word search, crossword, spot the ball, spot the difference etc.)
Footer	Link to website and social media channels
	Contact details (for newsletter and project)
	Appropriate references to CIVITAS & H2020

Newsletter content schedule

Within a limited number of issues, the newsletter must give a fair treatment to the breadth of subject matter of the GreenCharge project. The newsletter must also be opportunistic in terms of tying into milestones that generate newsworthy content over the course of the project.

It is proposed that, as far as possible, each work package is given a headline article slot. This is fitted as closely as possible to the milestones within the project. The planning of the newsletters and their planned theme can be found in table 8.

Table 8: Newsletter planning and themes

Newsletter No.	Month	Theme
1	6	Project presentation (incl. pilot cities) and roles of the partners involved in GreenCharge
2	14	Business models and prototypes for cities
3	18	Technology and management
4	26	Getting the Right Stakeholders including the Public/Users on Board
5	30	SUMPS and electric mobility
6	36	Summary and Goodbye

Informed Cities Newsletter

It is intended (and referenced in the Grant Agreement) that the GreenCharge newsletter will “make use of” the Informed Cities newsletter. Our concept for this is displayed below. Essentially, GreenCharge will be heavily profiled (alongside other mobility projects) in the Informed Cities Newsletter, but there would be a click-through to a separate and subordinate GreenCharge newsletter which is branded separately and contains a fuller range of stories dedicated to GreenCharge. In the first Informed Cities Newsletter, GreenCharge would be given a significant headline slot.

The screenshot shows the first page of the 'Electric Mobility Newsletter' (Issue 1 | February 2019). It features the GreenCharge logo and a headline: 'A Warm Welcome to Advances in Electric Mobility and Green Energy'. The main article is titled 'I suppose you know the story about how the emperor Nero played his fiddle while Rome burned?' and is written by Joe Gorman, Project Coordinator. A quote from Gorman states: 'GreenCharge takes us a few important steps closer to achieving one of the dreams of modern cities: a zero emission transport system based on electric vehicles running on green energy, with traffic jams and parking problems becoming things of the past.' The page also includes contact information for Joe Gorman and a link to the Informed Cities website.

The screenshot shows the second page of the newsletter, featuring a 'Feature Article: Introduction to GreenCharge eMobility in Bremen, Barcelona and Oslo'. It includes a map of Europe highlighting the pilot cities. A quote from the article reads: 'Electric scooter sharing is an innovative element in order to reduce car use.' The page also features a photo of an electric scooter and a list of EV types: Type of EV, Energy, and Location. The footer includes the website address www.greencharge.eu/001/en.

Figure 4-4: Some GreenCharge Newsletter Screenshots

4.4 Brochures and presentations

Since the beginning of the project, logos, brochures, posters and common templates for presentations and other actions were planned to be developed to create brand identity, consistency and awareness of the project. Brochures will contain a short project description and will be used during events to inform stakeholders and motivate them to become part of the GreenCharge community. Therefore, the project already created three project logos⁶ (see Figure 4-4, Figure 4-5 & Figure 4-6), different templates for the presentation of the project and a template for the deliverables. This style will be used for all future communication material productions. Additionally, a brochure was already designed (see Figure 4-7).

Figure 4-4: Coloured GreenCharge logo

Figure 4-5: Black-and-white GreenCharge logo

Figure 4-6: GreenCharge supporter logo

⁶ Link to Project logos: <https://sintef.sharepoint.com/teams/work-5401/Core%20Project%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fteams%2Fwork%2D5401%2FCore%20Project%20Documents%2FProject%20Promotion%2FLogos>

Figure 4-7: GreenCharge brochure

4.5 Social media (Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn and Vimeo)

Social media will be covered by Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn and Vimeo. The channels will be used for focused communications on the achievements of the project and to show presented webinars. All social media tools will reach different target audiences. Mutual links from partners’ websites and other organizations with interest in this area will also be displayed. A short link to the project Twitter account is already on the project website (see Figure 4-1). The twitter account is <https://twitter.com/GreenCharge2020>. The GreenCharge LinkedIn page can be found on <https://www.linkedin.com/company/greencharge-project/>. To use Twitter and LinkedIn correctly several things are to be considered and will be explained in detail in Chapter 5.2 and 5.3.

A social media grid will be drawn that will plot the most appropriate social media channel/sites for targeting specific audiences. This will go beyond using the media as just another way to “put out messages”: we recognise the opportunity that social media offers for *interaction* with the wider community (people can e.g. respond to posts, re-tweet with remarks etc). Social media channels will be actively monitored by project partners and used for *dialogue* with interested parties. This will help create ‘communities of support’ for the project. We will use techniques such as videos, animations, info-graphic imagery, mobile enabled content and richer content experiences. We will also identify GreenCharge digital ‘champions’ in the pilots and use the contact networks from project partners (especially ICLEI). The quantitative and qualitative targets that are defined for the social media communications are listed in table 11 (chapter 5).

Content

Social media accounts can be used for communication about:

- Organization of meetings (open days, consortium meeting)
- Achieving milestones
- News and blogposts published on the website (to increase website traffic)
- World news about relevant project topics
- Public deliverables (including download links)
- Newsletters (increase visibility)

Above is only a small list of possible communication topics. It is important to place content with a direct and clear link to the project topics at the GreenCharge social media accounts. The number of followers and the traffic on the project website and social media pages will increase when the content is updated frequently.

Analytics and monitoring

For assessing their effectiveness, the project’s social media accounts will be monitored by using Twitter analytics.

4.6 Lectures of students and academics

The Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli (SUN) interest in project results is related to their own students. The results of GreenCharge will be immediately exploited in teaching by involving master students of UiO directly on project related topics, and on the topics taught in the course *INF5870 - Energy Informatics* covering computing and communications technologies and their applications for sustainable energy sectors - e.g., smart grid, solar, electric vehicles, and storage. This course lay the foundations to understand where and how computer engineering techniques apply in the energy systems.

4.7 A movie/animation about GreenCharge

An animated video is planned about the GreenCharge project. This animation will be published at the website and promoted through the social media channels of the project. The creation of a movie/animation is a perfect way of visualising the GreenCharge project and making it understandable in a quick way. It also is a great way of easily spreading the GreenCharge concept. The movie/animation is expected to be delivered in the second half of 2019.

4.8 Events

Several external events are planned during the lifetime of the project. This includes self-organised events like workshops, a GreenCharge conference, webinars and open days. Also, the GreenCharge project will be present at different external events in the mobility sector. The search of relevant events is ongoing and will continue until the end of the project. The results of the search are posted on the project website to promote an active participation by both, partners and external contacts.

4.8.1 External Events

GreenCharge will ensure that results are communicated at relevant international conferences/workshops. The project will present the SUMP approach at city-related events of the EC like CIVITAS Forum, Transport Research Arena (TRA) etc. In addition, relevant industrial / interest group events may be used. We have identified a preliminary list of potentially relevant events which can be found in Appendix A.

4.8.2 Self-organised events

GreenCharge partners will self-organised several events of different types. This includes a GreenCharge conference, workshops, open days and webinars.

GreenCharge conference. During year 3 of the GreenCharge project, a larger (approx. 150 participants) 1.5-day Informed Cities conference will convene project partners and Uptake Cities with a cross-European mix of participants from local government (at least 25 cities from 15 European countries), academia, business, NGOs and other organisations, to share and contest the project outcomes. Coordinated by ICLEI, the consortium will dedicate one edition of the established conference series 'Informed Cities' to the GreenCharge project. ICLEI will co-develop the programme together with the project partners, involving also other relevant H2020 projects of the same thematic area.

Workshops have been planned to develop business models in Bremen, Barcelona and Oslo. In addition, a workshop at the ICNC (International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications) Conference is planned.

Open days. The project will arrange plenary meetings approximately every 8 months, each lasting 3-4 days. These are primarily intended for coordination of work within the consortium itself. Once a year, one full day of such meetings will be designated as the "open day". A selected group of external stakeholders will be invited to each open day; some time will be used for presentation of the project, but most time will be used for an open dialogue between the consortium partners and the external stakeholders. The presence of most key members of the project allows the arrangement of detailed one-to-one discussions on specific topics on an *ad hoc* basis.

Webinars. GreenCharge will hold at least 3 webinars during the project duration at M6, M18, and M34. These will be a 30-40-minute talk by 1-2 members of the consortium on project topics. This will be followed by 20-

30 minutes of questions and answers by attendees. Webinars will be recorded and uploaded to the project's website to YouTube, Vimeo etc. The aim is to offer the workshops on demand, unbound by time or location, and thereby limiting the environmental impact of attending such an event.

4.9 Networking with other groups

Cooperation and synergies will be established/created with European-wide communities:

- EU initiatives to facilitate the exchange of best practices and the deployment of new technologies at the local (city) level. Possible partners are the Covenant of Mayors, the Smart Cities and Communities European Innovation Partnership and the CIVITAS initiative for cleaner and better transport in cities. The exact requirements for CIVITAS will be set out in detail in an updated version of the CIVITAS Corporate Design Handbook.
- The EU Platform on Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, which provides assistance and a venue for cooperation and exchange of experiences for the relevant actors and stakeholders (www.mobilityplans.eu).
- The European Alternative Fuels Observatory, which has been set up to support the monitoring of the market up-take of alternatively fuelled vehicles, as well as the Sustainable Transport Forum to support the CPT implementation (<http://www.eafo.eu/>).

These cooperations can be established through attending relevant events which are organised or attended by the groups described above. The GreenCharge consortium is also connected via social media with the European network groups.

5 Communication Guidelines

Partners are requested to communicate about the project through their corporate channels (e.g. social media accounts, like Twitter and LinkedIn, website, newsletter, printed materials or announcements) as much as possible. Partners are also required to contact local media and other interest groups to raise awareness of the project.

As mentioned in Chapter 4.1 any dissemination and communication activity related to the project (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any major results funded by the grant will:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

For communication activities: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769016”.

It is important to make regular recurrent reporting, e.g. participation at an event, completing an excel file to fill in all events partner suggested to attend as GreenCharge partner. If the decision is made to attend an event the partner should do the following:

- inform immediately PNO and their own communication experts to put the event on the website and other channels
- inform stakeholders at least four weeks in advance about the attendance, this could be a very good opportunity to meet project partners and get informed about the project.

5.1 Guidelines for written content

The GreenCharge sharepoint (*Working documents* → *Workpackages* → *WP 8 Maximisation of impact* → *Draft Project Descriptions*) can be used for standard texts about the project and the project objectives. These standard texts can be used for external communication and can be disseminated through different channels (e.g. corporate website or corporate newsletter). If a project partner wants to release self-written communication about the GreenCharge project, they should consider the following hints:

- clear and comprehensible communication
- short sentences
- vocabulary suitable for target audience
- receive attention with a picture
- target audience relevant aspects.

5.2 Guidelines for using Twitter

Recommendations on how to use Twitter (tweets for the GreenCharge account or tweets mentioning the GreenCharge project from your own or company Twitter account).

What should be post?

Text of up to 280 characters. This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying someone else's tweet within your own) but includes links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).

What should a post look like?

To share short comments, make announcements that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweet relevant content, consider the following:

- Tag (# or @) your publisher/event organizer, to reach a wider audience
- #: Using a hashtag makes the keyword or phrase in the post searchable. It is like a label that clusters and links similar content, the same way keywords do when scientific papers are published. This makes it easier

for users to locate specific content or topics. However, hashtags cannot be followed, i.e., users will not be informed, when a new tweet related to this hashtag has been posted.

@: Unique user name mainly used to identify a person or a project’s account. It always starts with the @ symbol, followed by a name or phrase to identify the account. Users can be followed. Thus, the follower is instantly notified when the users posts new tweets or likes other tweets.

- Use #H2020 and/or @EU_H2020: Be part of the online conversation about Horizon 2020 and your tweets become searchable
- Please add “#GreenCharge2020” or @GreenCharge2020” on relevant posts of own accounts to be retweeted
- Use #electromobility: Tweets about GreenCharge always belong to electromobility; and
- Tweet by using #CIVITAS_GreenCharge2020 and include in each tweet reference to @CIVITAS_EU then it will be picked up by CIVITAS channels
- Link to your papers/articles/press releases in your tweets
- Include emojis in your tweets
- Twitter is becoming increasingly visual — post pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualisations to spark interest
- Check the user/project profiles you follow for their individual hashtags; use these hashtags in your tweets to gain more attention, followers and potential collaboration
- Try to consider to post times during high engagement times (see Figure 5-1)

Figure 5-1: Twitter engagement times⁷

Connect with other Horizon 2020 beneficiaries & follow the European Commission social media channels

Projects under the same call often share goals and are aimed at similar audiences. By connecting and clustering with likeminded beneficiaries — for example, by following their account, retweeting or replying to their posts or tagging them — you can attract each other’s followers and fans, enlarging your community of interested individuals and organisations.

⁷ <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/best-times-to-post-on-social-media/#twitter>. There are different figures for different target groups. This figure is focused on global engagement.

The EC also generally encourages beneficiaries to play an active role in Horizon 2020 communication and dissemination campaigns launched by the European Commission. The social media platforms of the Commission and its agencies can help you expand your audience by sharing your posts or liking your Tweets.

It is also useful to follow the GreenCharge consortium partners on Twitter. The Twitter account of the consortium partners can be found in table 9.

Useful Twitter accounts

- [@CIVITAS_EU](#) > CIVITAS account. The network of cities across Europe dedicated to sustainable urban transport the GreenCharge project does corporation with
- [@CORDIS_EU](#) > Official CORDIS account. News and information on EU-funded research projects & results
- [@EU_Commission](#) > News and information from the European Commission
- [@EU_H2020](#) > Official account for EU's #H2020 & future #HorizonEU research & innovation programme
- [@inea_eu](#) > Official account for Innovation & Networks Executive Agency

Table 9 : Twitter accounts of GreenCharge consortium members

	Consortium member	Twitter account
1	SINTEF AS	@SINTEF
2	eSmart Systems AS	@eSmart_Systems
3	Hubject GmbH	@hubject
4	FUNDACIO EURECAT	@Eurecat_news
5	Atlantis IT S.L.U	@AtlantisIT
6	Millor Energy Solutions SL - Enchufing	@Enchufing_com
7	Motit World SL	
8	Freie Hansestadt Bremen	@bremen_de
9	Move About GmbH	
10	Personal Mobility Center Nordwest eG	@pmc_nordwest
11	Oslo kommune	
12	FORTUM	@Fortum
13	PNO Consultants BV PNO Consultants GmbH (Third Partner)	@PNOconsultants @foerderberatung
14	Università della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”	
15	University of Oslo	@UniOslo
16	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH	@ICLEI_Europe

5.3 Guidelines for using LinkedIn

Short recommendations on how to use LinkedIn (posts about GreenCharge in the project’s LinkedIn site and your own LinkedIn profiles with posts mentioning the GreenCharge project).

What can you post?

Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.

How to use LinkedIn?

A networking site for professionals, it can be used to join groups and discuss with group members (experts, stakeholders) and has established networks on specific topics. Several projects have chosen LinkedIn to create new groups, share content and connect with already established groups.

GreenCharge also has its own LinkedIn project page. This page can be found on <https://www.linkedin.com/company/greencharge-project/>. It is recommended for project partners to follow this LinkedIn page and to share or react on posts to increase the visibility of GreenCharge project. Before using social media, it is mandatory to read the Horizon 2020 social media guidelines of the European Commission.⁸ It is also useful to follow the company LinkedIn accounts of the consortium partners. Their LinkedIn accounts can be found in table 10.

The rules and utilization of “#” and “@” are similar to Twitter (see Chapter 5.2). Please consider the highest engagement times to post on LinkedIn (see Figure 5-2).

Project partners can also sign up to the CIVITAS LinkedIn Urban Mobility Group: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4286016/profile>.

Table 10: LinkedIn accounts of GreenCharge consortium members

	Consortium member	LinkedIn account
1	SINTEF AS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sintef/
2	eSmart Systems AS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/esmart-systems/
3	Hubject GmbH	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hubject/
4	FUNDACIO EURECAT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/
5	Atlantis IT S.L.U	https://www.linkedin.com/company/atlantisit/
6	Millor Energy Solutions SL - Enchufing	
7	Motit World SL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/motit-barcelona/ (Barcelona department of Motit)
8	Freie Hansestadt Bremen	
9	Move About GmbH	
10	Personal Mobility Center Northwest eG	
11	Oslo kommune	https://www.linkedin.com/company/oslo-kommune/

⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

	Consortium member	LinkedIn account
12	FORTUM	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fortum/life/
13	PNO Consultants BV PNO Consultants GmbH	https://www.linkedin.com/company/pno-consultants/ https://www.linkedin.com/company/pno-consultants-gmbh/
14	Università della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universitaluigivanvitelli/about/
15	University of Oslo	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universitetet-i-oslo/
16	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH	

In addition, if project partners have Facebook accounts, they can sign up to the CIVITAS Facebook page, which can be found at: <https://www.facebook.com/Civitas-Initiative-35555381152607/>.

Figure 5-2: LinkedIn engagement times⁹

5.4 Guidelines for handling privacy issues

Ethics guidelines and data management principles in GreenCharge are defined in D9.1 POPD - Requirement no. 1 and D1.1 Data Management Plan. Aspects relevant for the website and newsletters are summarized below.

Privacy statement

Some of the contact information to external parties will be totally curated and preserved by one partner. The dissemination partners PNO Consultants and ICLEI do have their own contact pre-existing lists that will be used for dissemination and communication purposes. These contact lists will not be shared within the project, but they will be managed according to GDPR by the partners.

⁹ <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/best-times-to-post-on-social-media/#twitter>

Contact information for other external actors established just for the purpose of the project will be managed within the project in accordance with GDPR:

- The contact information will be managed in separate lists depending on purpose, e.g.
 - Contact lists for local reference groups
 - Contact list for Uptake Cities Group
 - Contact list for pilot site participants
 - Contact list for recipients of dissemination and communication material
- All project generated contact lists will be stored in the GreenCharge sharepoint project site hosted by SINTEF. Access control will be implemented. Only those needing the contact information will have access to it. For example, only the pilot coordinators will have access to information about the local reference groups.
- The information will not be shared with third parties.
- The purpose of the contact information will be stated for each contact list.
- Only information needed will be kept and managed.
- The statuses with respect to consents will be managed when relevant.
- On request from external parties, there will be routines for
 - Provision of information on the personal information the project is managing.
 - Deletion of contact information for distribution of information (e.g. for distribution of newsletters).
 - Deletion of contact information when consents are not provided or withdrawn (in such cases the related data collected from the pilots will also be deleted).

When information from the project is disseminated, the recipients will be informed about how they can get in contact with the project and how they can withdraw from the contact list.

Website

PNO Consultants is responsible for privacy issues with respect to the communication channels and contact lists and can be reached by email at gdpr@pnoconsultants.com. The GreenCharge Privacy Statement is in line with the GDPR and applies to all persons for whom GreenCharge processes personal data. Personal data are all data that contains information about persons with which those persons are identifiable. The Privacy Statement applies to:

- Visitors to the GreenCharge website
- Invitations to events/workshops
- Recipients of newsletters and commercial e-mails from GreenCharge
- Any other person who contacts GreenCharge or whose personal data is processed by GreenCharge.

GreenCharge respects the personal data (e.g. contact list, subscribers to the newsletter) and ensures that the personal information provided to GreenCharge or otherwise obtained is treated confidentially. Personal data is all information about a person. Data that indirectly says something about someone is also personal data.

To analyse the use of the communication channels, GreenCharge will process personal data that people have provided, personal data generated during visiting the website and reading newsletters and personal data that GreenCharge has derived from other sources, such as business social media platforms and business cards. The results from the processing will however be anonymized before they are shared within the project and outside the project.

The GreenCharge website may contain hyperlinks to websites of other parties and social media buttons. GreenCharge is not responsible for the content of those websites or the services of relevant social media platforms. Nor is GreenCharge responsible for the privacy policy and the use of cookies on those websites and social media platforms.

GreenCharge do not store personal data for longer than is strictly necessary for the execution of the purposes. If legal regulations apply to the storage, the personal data will not be kept longer than prescribed by law.

The complete GreenCharge Privacy Statement can be read on <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/privacy-policy/>. The GreenCharge cookie statement can be found on <https://www.pnoconsultants.com/cookie-policy/>.

Newsletter

By subscribing to the newsletter and providing their details, people agree to receive the Informed Cities newsletter. GreenCharge will never sell peoples' data or pass it on to anyone else. GreenCharge will only share the data with Mailchimp, the company that provides GreenCharge's mailing software. Mailchimp will only use this data for sending the newsletter. By subscribing to the newsletter, people acknowledge that the information they provide will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing in accordance with their own privacy policy and terms. The subscription is only confirmed after clicking the link in the confirmation e-mail.

This consent will form the lawful basis of the processing of peoples' data. People can unsubscribe, ask GreenCharge to update their information or ask to delete their information from the records at any time by contacting newsletter@informedcities.eu.

6 Key performance indicators

The detailed Communication Strategy and Plan produced in the project defines quantitative and qualitative targets to assess and measure communication impact. An initial summary of the KPIs and their targets is shown below.

Table 11: Key Performance Indicators on communication activities

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Means of verification
Website	Number of unique visits	3,000	Google analytics
	Number of registered for upload	500	Google analytics
	Number of downloads of content	200	Google analytics
	Number of subscribers for the newsletter	200	Communication report in D8.2
Press coverage	Number of EU wide press releases	8	Copies of press releases
	Number of slots/articles	12	Copies of slots/articles
Publications	Number of newsletters	6	Copies of newsletters
	Number of scientific/technical publications	6	Copies of scientific/technical publications
	Number of brochures spreaded	300	Copies of brochures
Twitter	Number of Tweets	200	Twitter analytics
	Number of followers	200	Twitter analytics
	Number of retweets	50	Twitter analytics
LinkedIn	Number of followers	200	LinkedIn analytics
	Number of unique visits	200	LinkedIn analytics
	Number of posts	18	LinkedIn analytics
YouTube	Number of project videos	1	Records of project videos
	Number of webinars	3	Records of webinars
	Number of views	500	Youtube analytics
	Number of subscribers	50	Youtube analytics
Networks	Number of uptake cities	12	Communication report in D8.2
	Number of reference groups	3	Communication report in D8.2
	Number of actors accessible through partner networks	469	Communication report in D8.2

Events	Number of large-scale events	1	Records of attendance, presentations
	Number of workshops	9	Report of workshops
	Number of open days	3	Records of attendance, presentations
	Number of conferences	20	Records of attendance, presentations

7 Roles and responsibilities

The communication strategy foresees the active involvement of all project partners. PNO, the WP8 lead beneficiary, is responsible for the communication activities and will ensure the proper information exchange within the consortium and support the full communication of the project's content and results.

The cost for communication materials and equipment is all allocated in PNO's budget for the whole project. This includes the printing of brochures, video recording equipment and special equipment for making the promotional animations, etc.

All consortium partners have an important role in the communication of project results and all the partners are committed to present project outcomes. The universities and RTOs are of great importance for providing scientific publications whilst the commercial partners are focused on the exploitation and dissemination part of the project communication (e.g. attending fairs or conferences). All partners will be actively involved in communication activities to emphasise the importance of the work, and to facilitate an effective communication at the local level at all locations covered by the consortium.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

The document aims to describe the measures proposed by the GreenCharge Consortium to effectively communicate project's activities and results.

The communication strategy constitutes an important management tool for both the project partnership and the European Commission, with upper aim to ensure that GreenCharge communication activities are sufficiently planned and implemented. It is an active document, which will be updated in future reports.

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The communication strategy constitutes an important management tool for both the project partnership and the European Commission, with upper aim to ensure that GreenCharge communication activities are sufficiently planned and implemented.

Different communication channels have been selected to efficiently address the different target groups derived from the Stakeholder Analysis. This will ensure effective community building and spreading the results of the GreenCharge project. Collaboration with other initiatives such as CIVITAS will help to achieve more engagement with potential stakeholders. Participation of partners is required to maximize the impact and visibility of the GreenCharge project. Activities have to be planned in advance to align operations and to ensure the stakeholder community is aware of the activities. Branding and image is important to make the GreenCharge project recognizable and rememberability of the GreenCharge Project.

As the project evolves, we will want to refine the Communication Strategy and Plan, for example to provide more details of planned events, possible contacts, communication channels etc, or to refine the strategy in other ways. We will do this by a mixture of:

- (a) Creating revised versions of this document that include the refined information;
- (b) Using other more direct mechanisms such as separate tables and list of events/contacts that can be stored in the cooperation tool used by the consortium.

Both (a) and (b) will be considered to fulfil the text about "Will be continuously refined during the project" in the formal description of the deliverable in the GA. Any updated versions of this document will be made available to the Commission on request, with "track changes" being used to show what has been updated. The contents of any separate tables etc. as defined in (b) can also be made available to the Commission on request.

A Appendix A

A.1 List of future events with potential for GreenCharge participation

Date	Event title (original title)	Location
19/03/2019	rEVolution	Amsterdam, The Netherlands
14/05 – 15/05/2019	Power2Drive Europe Conference 2019	Munich, Germany
14/05 – 15/05/2019	World Light Electric Vehicle Summit 2019	Lisbon, Portugal
19/05 – 22/05/2019	International Electric Vehicle Symposium & Exhibition (EVS 32)	Lyon, France
22/05 – 24/05/2019	Urban Future Global Conference	Oslo, Norway
29/05 – 01/06/2019	ECOMM 2019 (European Conference on Mobility Management)	Edinburgh, Scotland
03/06 – 06/06/2019	ITS European Congress	Brainport, The Netherlands
09/06 – 12/06/2019	Global Public Transport Summit	Stockholm, Sweden
13/06 – 14/06/2019	Intercharge Network Conference (ICNC)	Berlin, Germany
17/06 – 18/06/2019	6th European Conference on SUMP	Groningen, The Netherlands
26/06 – 27/06/2019	Oxford EV Summit	Oxford, United Kingdom
02/10 – 04/10/2019	CIVITAS Forum	Graz, Austria
07/10 – 11/10/2019	Walk21 Conference	Rotterdam, The Netherlands
09/10/2019	Annual Electric Vehicle Event	Edinburgh, Scotland
16/10 – 17/10/2019	Autonomy & The Urban Mobility Summit	Paris, France
21/10 – 25/10/2019	ITS World Congress	Singapore
06/11 – 07/11/2019	1 st Nordic ZEB+	Trondheim, Norway
12/11 – 13/11/2019	Grid Integration of Electric Mobility 2019 (ATZ conference)	Stuttgart, Germany
12/11 – 14/11/2019	European Utility Week	Paris, France
19/11 – 21/11/2019	Smart City Expo World Congress	Barcelona, Spain
27/11 – 28/11/2019	POLIS conference	Brussels, Belgium
27/04 – 30/04/2020	Transport Research Arena	Helsinki, Finland
tbd	Startup Fest Europe	

tbd	IEEE Systems of Systems Engineering Conference	
tbd	ICLEI World Congress	
tbd	EcoMobility World Congress	
tbd	9th European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns	

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